

5

Symbolic Execution

In this chapter, we formally define the symbolic execution approach implemented by MAZE. We begin by defining the symbolic state representation, auxiliary functions, and other preliminaries in Section 5.1. Section 5.2 then presents an operational semantics that precisely describes the execution of a program based on transition rules for different Jimple statements.

5.1 Preliminaries

5.1.1 Execution over Jimple Statements

The symbolic execution in MAZE operates on the Jimple IR and traverses CFGs constructed from Jimple statements, such as the one in Figure 4.4. As described in Section 4.5.1, Jimple is a simplified three-address representation of JVM bytecode, where no statement contains nested expressions. As a result, each Jimple statement typically corresponds to a single bytecode instruction. For instance, rather than representing an entire `if-then-else` construct as a compound statement, Jimple models only the conditional `if` statement containing the guard expression. In the corresponding CFG, this statement has two outgoing edges: one for the true branch and one for the false branch.

This structure eliminates the need for transition rules to handle nested constructs, simplifying their definitions. Additionally, the composition of Jimple CFGs means the semantics need not account for certain language-specific behaviors such as Java’s `switch-case` fall-through; these are accurately captured in the CFG. Lastly, rules for `while` and `for` loops are unnecessary, as these constructs are desugared into `if` statements and `goto` instructions in JVM bytecode, and thus do not appear explicitly in Jimple.

5.1.2 Symbolic State Representation

The symbolic execution state encapsulates all information needed to represent a program at a specific point in its execution. We define the symbolic state S as a tuple:

$$S = \langle s, m, d, \sigma, \pi, \rho, H, A, R, C, f_{\text{fin}}, f_{\text{exc}}, f_{\text{ctor}} \rangle$$

where:

- s : the next statement to execute.
- m : the method to which s belongs.
- d : the execution depth.
- σ : the store, mapping variable names to symbolic expressions, i.e., $\sigma : \text{Var} \mapsto \text{Expr}$.
- ρ : the return value of the current or previously invoked method.
- π : the set of path constraints accumulated along the execution path.
- H : the heap, mapping concrete references to heap objects, i.e., $H : \text{ConcreteRef} \mapsto \text{HeapObject}$.
- A : the alias map, mapping symbolic references to sets of concrete references that they may alias, i.e., $A : \text{SymbolicRef} \mapsto \{\text{ConcreteRef}\}$.

- R : the set of symbolic references that have been resolved to a single concrete alias.
- C : the caller state, i.e., the symbolic state from which the current method m was invoked.
- f_{fin} : a Boolean flag indicating whether the state has reached the end of the MUT.
- f_{exc} : a Boolean flag indicating whether execution has entered an exceptional state (i.e., whether an exception would be thrown at this point in concrete execution).
- f_{exc} : a Boolean flag indicating whether the current method is the constructor of the CUT where execution was initiated.

We distinguish between *symbolic references* (SymbolicRef, typically denoted r_s) and *concrete references* (ConcreteRef, typically denoted r_c). The engine uses concrete references to index the heap, i.e., to retrieve a heap object $H(r_c) = O$, where O is a HeapObject as defined below. A symbolic reference may alias one or more concrete references, as recorded in the alias map A . When a symbolic reference r_s is used in a statement, it is resolved to one of these concrete references—ensuring it is associated with a single heap object when dereferenced—and added to the set R to record that it has been resolved. If a symbolic reference represents a null reference, its corresponding concrete reference would be a constant defined as null.

A HeapObject can take one of the following forms:

- **Regular Object:** $O_{\text{obj}}(\tau, F)$, where τ denotes the object’s type and F maps field names to symbolic values.
- **Array Object:** $O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, E, \ell)$, where τ is the array type, E is the symbolic array containing the array’s values, and ℓ is the symbolic array length. Note that the symbolic array E has no inherent notion of length on its own; it represents a purely symbolic mapping from indices to values. Hence, we need a separate value for the length.

Given a symbolic state $S = \langle s, m, d, \sigma, \pi, \rho, H, A, R, C, f_{\text{fin}}, f_{\text{exc}}, f_{\text{ctor}} \rangle$, we adopt the notation c_S to refer to component c of state S . That is, we assume that each rule implicitly unpacks the state as $S = \langle s_S, m_S, d_S, \sigma_S, \pi_S, \rho_S, H_S, A_S, R_S, C_S, (f_{\text{fin}})_S, (f_{\text{exc}})_S, (f_{\text{ctor}})_S \rangle$. For instance, π_S refers to the path constraints of state S . This convention avoids repetitive tuple unpacking in each transition rule.

This formalization omits handling of multi-dimensional arrays for brevity. Section 4.4.2 discusses the practical handling of multi-dimensional arrays by MAZE.

Additionally, this representation slightly simplifies the treatment of symbolic constraints. While the engine internally maintains separate lists for path constraints and engine-specific constraints (used for limiting solving time or soundness guarantees), this formalization unifies both under the single constraint set π for clarity and brevity.

5.1.3 Trace Entries and Replay

As discussed in Section 4.6, MAZE’s concrete-driven execution records a trace during concrete execution, which it later uses for symbolic replay. In our formalization, a trace entry θ is defined as a tuple:

$$\theta = \langle \beta, v \rangle$$

where:

- β : the branch type, where $\beta \in \{\text{IF}, \text{SWITCH}, \text{ARRAY}, \text{ALIAS}\}$, consistent with the format introduced in Section 4.6.
- v : the value encoding the branch outcome:
 - IF: 0 (false) or 1 (true).
 - SWITCH: index of the case taken.
 - ARRAY: 0 (out-of-bounds) or 1 (in-bounds).
 - ALIAS: -1 (null reference) or parameter index.

Let \mathcal{T} denote the globally available sequence of trace entries. We define a function $\text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m)$ to consume the next trace entry from \mathcal{T} for method m :

$$\text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m) = \begin{cases} \langle \beta, v \rangle & \text{if a next entry exists for } m, \\ \perp & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We write $\text{ex}.P(x)$ to denote some (arbitrary) x such that $P(x)$ holds, if one exists. This convention is used in some of the rules for symbolic replay to, e.g., select a single successor statement to follow from a set of successors.

5.1.4 Auxiliary Functions

Evaluation We define an evaluation function $\llbracket v \rrbracket_S$ that transforms a Jimple value v into its corresponding symbolic expression e in the context of a symbolic state S :

$$\llbracket v \rrbracket_S = \begin{cases} \text{toSym}(c) & \text{if } v \text{ is a constant } c, \\ \sigma_S(v) & \text{if } v \text{ is a local variable,} \\ \text{toSym}(\neg)(\llbracket x \rrbracket_S) & \text{if } v = \neg x, \\ \text{toSym}(\oplus)(\llbracket x \rrbracket_S, \llbracket y \rrbracket_S) & \text{if } v = x \oplus y \text{ for a binary operator } \oplus. \end{cases}$$

Here, $\text{toSym}(x)$ is a function that converts a Jimple constant or operator x into its equivalent symbolic expression. In the context of MAZE, for example, integer values are converted to Z3 bit vectors. While this definition covers the basic Jimple constructs, other types of Jimple values, such as array creation expressions, require additional handling. These cases are addressed separately with dedicated transition rules.

We use tuple-indexed notation like $(\llbracket v_i \rrbracket_S = e_i)_{i=1}^n$ to compactly express a sequence of similar expressions or evaluations over a fixed range $1, \dots, n$. This notation is not limited to evaluation functions and may be applied to any sequence of related expressions.

Control Flow We define the function $\text{succ}(s)$ to denote the set of successor statements of a statement s within its Jimple CFG, which may contain zero or more statements $s' \in \text{succ}(s)$:

$$\text{succ}(s) = \{s' \mid \text{an edge exists from } s \text{ to } s' \text{ in the CFG containing } s\}$$

In addition, we define the function $\text{csucc}(s) \subseteq \text{succ}(s)$ to capture those successors that represent the entry points of catch blocks in a try-catch construct:

$$\text{csucc}(s) = \{s' \in \text{succ}(s) \mid s' \text{ is the first statement of a catch block}\}$$

The function $\text{entry}(m)$ provides the first statement in a method m .

New State We define the function $\text{newState}(m)$ to construct a fresh symbolic state for a given method m :

$$\text{newState}(m) = \langle \text{entry}(m), m, 0, \emptyset, \emptyset, \perp, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \perp, \perp, \perp, \perp \rangle$$

Note that \perp is used to represent both a false value for Boolean flags and the absence of a particular entity, such as the return value and the caller state.

References We define the function $\text{refs}(S)$ to extract all symbolic references that occur in the operands of the current statement s_S of the given state S :

$$\text{refs}(S) = \{r \mid r \text{ is a symbolic reference occurring in } s_S\}$$

This finds all variables in s referencing objects or arrays, and retrieves their symbolic references from the store σ of S . For example, consider a symbolic state S_e :

$$S_e = \langle x = \text{obj} \cdot y, m, d, \{\text{obj} \mapsto r_s\}, \emptyset, \perp, \{r_c \mapsto O_{\text{obj}}(\tau, F)\}, \{r_s \mapsto \{r_c, \text{null}\}\}, \emptyset, \perp, \perp, \perp, \perp \rangle$$

The current statement of S_e contains an (unresolved) object reference obj , meaning $\text{refs}(S_e) = \{r_s\}$.

Building on this, we define the function $\text{uref}(S)$ to retrieve the first unresolved symbolic reference in statement s_S with respect to the set of resolved references R_S of symbolic state S :

$$\text{uref}(S) = \min\{r \in \text{refs}(S) \mid r \notin R_S\}$$

Here, \min denotes the leftmost occurrence according to the syntactic structure of r . This function facilitates the resolution of symbolic references during symbolic execution by identifying the next unresolved reference within a statement. In our example, $\text{uref}(S_e) = r_s$, as the symbolic reference r_s is not resolved, i.e., $r_s \notin R_{S_e}$.

We define the function $\text{newRef}()$ to generate a fresh symbolic or concrete reference. In practice, the engine maintains a heap counter to ensure reference uniqueness, though this mechanism is abstracted away in our formalization.

Furthermore, we define the function $\text{findAliases}(\tau, H)$ to return the set of concrete references in the heap H that point to objects of type τ :

$$\text{findAliases}(\tau, H) = \{r_c \mid H(r_c) = O \wedge (O = O_{\text{obj}}(\tau', F) \vee O = O_{\text{arr}}(\tau', E, \ell)) \wedge \tau' = \tau\}$$

We use this function to find potential aliases for symbolic references.

Type Classification To indicate that a type τ belongs to a particular category, we write $\tau \in \text{TypeCategory}$, where TypeCategory is one of the following sets:

- $\text{PrimitiveType} = \{\text{String}, \text{int}, \text{long}, \text{short}, \text{byte}, \text{char}, \text{boolean}, \text{float}, \text{double}\}$.
- $\text{ObjectType} = \{\text{List}, \text{MyClass}, \dots\}$.
- $\text{ArrayType} = \{\text{int}[], \text{boolean}[], \text{MyClass}[], \dots\}$.
- $\text{ReferenceType} = \text{ObjectType} \cup \text{ArrayType}$.

Note that String is treated as a primitive type in this system.

Symbolic Value Creation We define the function $\text{newArr}(\tau)$ to construct a fresh symbolic array whose elements are of type τ . In practice, this corresponds to a Z3 array with integer indices and a range sort matching the type τ .

The function $\text{newVar}(\tau)$ constructs a fresh, unconstrained symbolic variable of type τ . In practice, this corresponds to a Z3 constant with a sort matching the type τ .

The function $\text{newObj}(\tau)$ creates a new HeapObject for the type τ :

$$\text{newObj}(\tau) = \begin{cases} O_{\text{obj}}(\tau, \emptyset) & \text{if } \tau \in \text{ObjectType} \\ O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, \text{newArr}(\tau), \text{newVar}(\text{int})) & \text{if } \tau \in \text{ArrayType} \end{cases}$$

Note that this assigns a symbolic value to the length of the array object, treating it as an unknown.

5.2 Operational Semantics

We now formalize symbolic execution as transitions between symbolic states. Each rule has the form:

$$\frac{\text{premises}}{S \rightarrow S'} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\text{premises}}{S \rightarrow S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n}$$

where the conclusion represents a transition from state S to one or more successor states.

We use the following notation for state updates:

- $S[c \mapsto v]$ represents a new state that is identical to S , except that component c is updated to value v .
- $S[c_1 \mapsto v_1, \dots, c_n \mapsto v_n]$ represents a new state where components c_1, \dots, c_n are updated to values v_1, \dots, v_n , respectively.
- For internal mappings such as σ or A within a state, $\sigma[x \mapsto v]$ represents an updated mapping where x gets value v , leaving all other entries unchanged. A compound update like $S[\sigma \mapsto \sigma_S[x \mapsto v]]$ denotes a state where the σ -component of S is updated accordingly.

When successor states are derived uniformly, we may use the single-transition notation for brevity, even when multiple successor statements exist. For example, to denote that each $s' \in \text{succ}(s)$ gives rise to a new symbolic state, we use:

$$\frac{s' \in \text{succ}(s)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s']}$$

In the transition rules, we often use a form of pattern matching to determine applicability. For example, a premise like $s_S = \text{if } (c) \text{ then } s_t \text{ else } s_f$ states that the rule applies only if the statement component of S matches this structure. We may also write $s_S \in \{l := r[i], l := r.f\}$ to match a rule to any of the statement structures in the given set. The syntax used in premises is a simplified, abstracted form of Jimple's syntax, chosen to highlight control-flow semantics more clearly.

The initial state for symbolic execution is defined as $\text{newState}(m)$, where m is either the MUT (for static methods) or an arbitrarily chosen constructor of the CUT (for instance methods). In the case where execution begins at the class constructor, the f_{ctor} flag is set to true. A transition rule is responsible for switching to all non-static MUTs once symbolic execution reaches the end of the constructor, as described by the symbolic-driven workflow in Section 4.1.1. As a result, there may be multiple initial states: one for each static method, and a single shared initial state for all non-static methods.

We begin by defining the rules for standard symbolic execution in Section 5.2.1, followed by the rules for symbolic replay in Section 5.2.2. Rules are applied in the order presented.

5.2.1 Standard Execution

In standard symbolic execution, the engine explores multiple execution paths simultaneously. Thus, each transition rule may produce multiple successor states for a given state S .

5.2.1.1 Conditional Statements

If Statement The transition rule for `if` statements creates two execution paths corresponding to the true and false branches of an `if` statement. For an `if` statement with condition c , the condition is evaluated to obtain a symbolic expression e . The state transitions to two successor states: one where e is assumed to hold and execution proceeds to the `then`-branch, and another where e is assumed not to hold and execution proceeds to the `else`-branch. In both cases, the corresponding assumption is added to the path constraints π .

$$\frac{s_S = \text{if } (c) \text{ then } s_t \text{ else } s_f \quad \llbracket c \rrbracket_S = e}{S \rightarrow \frac{S[s \mapsto s_t, d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{e\}]}{S[s \mapsto s_f, d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{\neg e\}]}}$$

Switch Statement The `switch` statement rule represents conditional branching to multiple execution paths based on the value of a key expression k . When encountering a `switch` statement, the key is evaluated to a symbolic expression e_k and $n + 1$ distinct successor states are created: one for each of the n case values v_i (where e_k is constrained to equal the case value), and an additional state for the default case (constrained by e_k not equaling any case value).

$$\frac{s_S = \text{switch } (k) \{v_1 \Rightarrow s_1, \dots, v_n \Rightarrow s_n, \text{default} \Rightarrow s_d\} \quad \llbracket k \rrbracket_S = e_k \quad (\llbracket v_i \rrbracket_S = e_i)_{i=1}^n}{S \rightarrow \frac{S[s \mapsto s_1, d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{e_k = e_1\}]}{\vdots} \frac{S[s \mapsto s_n, d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{e_k = e_n\}]}{S[s \mapsto s_d, d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{\bigwedge_{i=1}^n e_k \neq e_i\}]}}$$

5.2.1.2 Exception Handling

Throw Statement When the execution encounters a statement that throws an exception, the symbolic state sets the exception flag to true. Subsequent application of the exception handling rule below determines whether a corresponding `catch` block is available.

$$\frac{s_S = \text{throw } e}{S \rightarrow S[f_{\text{exc}} \mapsto \top]}$$

Null Dereference This rule captures the case where an object or array is dereferenced through a null reference, leading to an exception. The rule applies to assignment statements where either the left-hand or right-hand side is a field access or array indexing operation on a reference r . The reference is evaluated to a symbolic reference r_s . If, according to the alias map A_S , r_s refers to the null reference `null`, this indicates a null dereference. In this case, the exception flag f_{exc} is set to \top , signaling that an exception would occur at this point in execution.

$$\frac{s_S \in \{l := r[i], l := r.f, r[i] := v, r.f := v\} \quad \llbracket r \rrbracket_S = r_s \quad r_s \in R_S \quad A_S(r_s) = \{\text{null}\}}{S \rightarrow S[f_{\text{exc}} \mapsto \top]}$$

Catching Exceptions The exception handling rule manages the control flow when the f_{exc} flag is true, i.e., when symbolic execution has identified the state as exceptional. The rule determines whether the current statement is within a `try-catch` construct by examining the set of catch block successors $\text{csucc}(s)$. For each potential exception handler, a new state is created where execution continues at the beginning of the `catch` block, the depth counter is incremented, and the exception flag is reset.

Having execution proceed to all available `catch` blocks aligns with the goals of symbolic execution, which aims to explore all possible execution paths. While explicit `throw` statements can indicate the type of exception being raised and thus which `catch` block should be followed, many exceptions are implicit (e.g., a division by zero). The types of such implicit exceptions depend on the JVM and are thus not statically recorded in the bytecode or Jimple, meaning symbolic execution cannot determine which exception handler to follow. Therefore, this rule does not inspect or match specific exception types to particular handlers.

$$\frac{f_{\text{exc}} = \top \quad \text{csucc}(s_S) \neq \emptyset \quad s' \in \text{csucc}(s_S)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s', d \mapsto d_S + 1, f_{\text{exc}} \mapsto \perp]}$$

If no `catch` block is available, the path is considered terminated, and the engine will generate a test case for it to trigger the exception.

$$\frac{f_{\text{exc}} = \top \quad \text{csucc}(s_S) = \emptyset}{S \rightarrow S[f_{\text{fin}} \mapsto \top]}$$

5.2.1.3 Alias Resolution

The alias resolution rule handles unresolved symbolic references occurring in a statement by resolving them to a single concrete reference from their alias set, thereby enabling dereferencing to a specific heap object. When the current statement s_S of state S contains a symbolic reference $r_s \notin R_S$ that may refer to a set of concrete references $\{r_c^1, \dots, r_c^n\}$ —as indicated by the alias map entry $A_S(r_s)$ —the rule forks the execution into n distinct successor states. Each successor resolves r_s to one of its candidate concrete references.

To resolve r_s to a specific concrete reference r_c^i , the rule updates the alias map by setting the value for r_s to the singleton set $\{r_c^i\}$, adds r_s to the resolved reference set R_S , and extends the PC with the constraint $r_s = r_c^i$. This operation does not advance execution to the next statement and thus does not increase the execution depth.

$$\frac{r_s = \text{uref}(S) \quad A_S(r_s) = \{r_c^1, \dots, r_c^n\}}{S[\pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{r_s = r_c^1\}, A \mapsto A_S[r_s \mapsto \{r_c^1\}], R \mapsto R_S \cup \{r_s\}], \\ S \rightarrow : \\ S[\pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{r_s = r_c^n\}, A \mapsto A_S[r_s \mapsto \{r_c^n\}], R \mapsto R_S \cup \{r_s\}]}$$

5.2.1.4 Return Statements

For `return` statements, execution either returns to the caller C if available, or it stops entirely because the end of a path has been reached, which is then marked by setting the f_{fin} flag to \top . If a caller is present, the path constraints π_S are copied back to the caller.

Value Return The rule for return statements that return a value v evaluate v to a symbolic expression e and bind that to the state's return value ρ .

$$\frac{s_S = \text{return } v \quad C_S = \perp \quad \llbracket v \rrbracket_S = e}{S \rightarrow S[\rho \mapsto e, f_{\text{fin}} \mapsto \top]}$$

$$\frac{s_S = \text{return } v \quad \llbracket v \rrbracket_S = e}{S \rightarrow C_S[\pi \mapsto \pi_S, \rho \mapsto e]}$$

Void Return When dealing with void returns, we simply omit setting the return value ρ .

$$\frac{s_S = \text{return void} \quad C_S = \perp}{S \rightarrow S[f_{\text{fin}} \mapsto \top]}$$

$$\frac{s_S = \text{return void}}{S \rightarrow C_S[\pi \mapsto \pi_S]}$$

End of Constructor Handling When symbolic execution reaches the end of the CUT's constructor, a special transition rule is applied. Rather than terminating execution, it transitions to every non-static MUT in the CUT. These are denoted $\{m' \in \mathcal{M} \mid \neg \text{isStatic}(m')\}$, where \mathcal{M} is the set of all MUTs for the current CUT. This rule resets the symbolic store to contain only the this binding, but preserves the heap to ensure that the constructed object and any objects or arrays transitively reachable through its fields remain accessible in the new execution context.

$$\frac{f_{\text{fin}} = \top \quad f_{\text{exc}} = \perp \quad f_{\text{ctor}} = \top \quad \{m' \in \mathcal{M} \mid \neg \text{isStatic}(m')\}}{S \rightarrow S[m \mapsto m', \sigma \mapsto \{\text{this} \mapsto \sigma_S(\text{this})\}, f_{\text{fin}} \mapsto \perp, f_{\text{ctor}} \mapsto \perp]}$$

5.2.1.5 Method Invocation

The method invocation rules formalize the transfer of control from a caller to a callee method during symbolic execution. This transition involves the creation of a new symbolic state corresponding to the callee method, along with the evaluation and binding of argument values and the transfer of relevant heap and aliasing information. The rules perform the following operations:

1. Create a new symbolic state S' , setting its current statement to the entry point of the method m being invoked.
2. Evaluate all arguments a_0, \dots, a_n to their symbolic values e_0, \dots, e_n .
3. Bind arguments to the new state's store σ' under canonical parameter names $\text{arg}_0, \dots, \text{arg}_n$.
4. Identify reference-type arguments—any a_i for which $e_i \in \text{refs}(S)$ —and collect their symbolic references r_s^1, \dots, r_s^k .
5. Map each symbolic reference r_s^j to its corresponding concrete reference r_c^j via the alias map A_S , assuming prior application of the alias resolution rule (Section 5.2.1.3) has resolved all such references to a single concrete reference (i.e., $r_s^j \in R_S$).
6. Extract the corresponding heap objects O^j from the caller's heap H_S , constructing a new heap

H' that includes those objects.

7. Construct a new alias map A' that maps each r_s^j to its concrete reference r_c^j .
8. Construct a new set R' of resolved references.
9. Transfer the caller's path constraints π_S to the new state to preserve the accumulated PC.
10. Record the caller state S in the new state to enable symbolic execution to return to it later.

In practice, the new state's heap H' also includes any heap objects transitively reachable through fields of object arguments or elements of array arguments. However, the rules omit these copies for brevity, as their inclusion would significantly increase the rule's complexity without affecting its core semantics.

We assume that the callee and caller share heap objects, so that updates to object fields or array elements in the callee are reflected in the caller. However, this does not account for the possibility that the callee may overwrite references to point to new heap objects. In practice, the engine uses shared heap objects during execution, but must copy any updated references back into the caller's state after the invocation to preserve such changes. This detail is omitted from the formal semantics for simplicity.

Static Method Invocation The rule below specifies this behavior for static method invocations, where m is invoked on a class literal `Class`.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 s_S = \text{Class}.m(a_0, \dots, a_n) \quad S' = \text{newState}(m) \\
 \frac{(\llbracket a_i \rrbracket_S = e_i)_{i=0}^n \quad \sigma' = \{\text{arg}_0 \mapsto e_0, \dots, \text{arg}_n \mapsto e_n\} \quad \{r_s^1, \dots, r_s^k\} = \{e_i \in \text{refs}(S) \mid 0 \leq i \leq n\} \\
 (r_s^j \in R_S)_{j=1}^k \quad (A_S(r_s^j) = \{r_c^j\})_{j=1}^k \quad (H_S(r_c^j) = O^j)_{j=1}^k \\
 H' = \{r_c^j \mapsto O^j \mid 1 \leq j \leq k\} \quad A' = \{r_s^j \mapsto \{r_c^j\} \mid 1 \leq j \leq k\} \quad R' = \{r_s^1, \dots, r_s^k\}}{S \rightarrow S'[\sigma \mapsto \sigma', \pi \mapsto \pi_S, H \mapsto H', A \mapsto A', R \mapsto R', C \mapsto S]}
 \end{array}$$

Instance Method Invocation For instance methods called on a base o , the rule must additionally incorporate the heap object and references associated with o , following the same procedure used for reference-type arguments. To maintain uniformity, the rule evaluates o to a symbolic reference e_{n+1} and processes it equivalently to reference-type arguments. The only semantic distinction from the static invocation rule is the binding of the symbolic reference e_{n+1} to the special variable `this` in the callee's store.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 s_S = o.m(a_0, \dots, a_n) \quad S' = \text{newState}(m) \quad (\llbracket a_i \rrbracket_S = e_i)_{i=0}^n \quad \llbracket o \rrbracket_S = e_{n+1} \\
 \sigma' = \{\text{arg}_0 \mapsto e_0, \dots, \text{arg}_n \mapsto e_n, \text{this} \mapsto e_{n+1}\} \quad \{r_s^1, \dots, r_s^k\} = \{e_i \in \text{refs}(S) \mid 0 \leq i \leq n+1\} \\
 (r_s^j \in R_S)_{j=1}^k \quad (A_S(r_s^j) = \{r_c^j\})_{j=1}^k \quad (H_S(r_c^j) = O^j)_{j=1}^k \\
 H' = \{r_c^j \mapsto O^j \mid 1 \leq j \leq k\} \quad A' = \{r_s^j \mapsto \{r_c^j\} \mid 1 \leq j \leq k\} \quad R' = \{r_s^1, \dots, r_s^k\}}{S \rightarrow S'[\sigma \mapsto \sigma', \pi \mapsto \pi_S, H \mapsto H', A \mapsto A', R \mapsto R', C \mapsto S]}
 \end{array}$$

5.2.1.6 Right-Hand Side of Assignment

Before defining the rules for assignment statements, we first specify rules for the various forms of right-hand side expressions in Jimple, including object creation, array creation, field access, array length, array indexing, method invocation, parameter references, local variables, and constants. Each rule evaluates the right-hand side and updates the current statement s in the state S by replacing the original right-hand side expression with its evaluated form e . To separate evaluation from assignment, the rules in this section abstract over the left-hand side, denoted generically as l . Specific handling of l is deferred to the next section, which introduces rules that complete the assignment by applying the evaluated right-hand side to the left-hand side l . This approach functions similarly to an evaluation context, though in a simplified and more direct form.

Object Allocation The transition rule for object allocation handles statements of the form $\text{new } \tau$, which allocate a fresh instance of class τ on the heap. This rule does not invoke a constructor—constructor calls are handled separately as method invocations in accordance with Jimple’s treatment of object initialization. This rule only performs the allocation of the object on the heap.

The rule generates a fresh symbolic reference r_s , and a fresh concrete reference r_c for the actual heap object. A new heap object O is created with type τ and an empty field map. The heap H is updated to map r_c to O , and the alias map A maps r_s to the singleton set $\{r_c\}$. That is, the new symbolic reference cannot alias an existing object, since a new statement explicitly creates a dedicated object for it.

$$\frac{s_S = l := \text{new } \tau \quad r_s = \text{newRef}() \quad r_c = \text{newRef}() \quad O = O_{\text{obj}}(\tau, \emptyset)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := r_s, H \mapsto H_S[r_c \mapsto O], A \mapsto A_S[r_s \mapsto \{r_c\}]}$$

Array Allocation The transition rule for array allocation handles expressions of the form $\text{new } \tau [n]$, which allocate a new array of element type τ and length n . It closely resembles the object allocation rule, but instead constructs an array object O with element type τ , length n , and contents represented by a fresh symbolic array generated via $\text{newArr}(\tau)$.

$$\frac{s_S = l := \text{new } \tau [n] \quad r_s = \text{newRef}() \quad r_c = \text{newRef}() \quad O = O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, \text{newArr}(\tau), n)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := r_s, H \mapsto H_S[r_c \mapsto O], A \mapsto A_S[r_s \mapsto \{r_c\}]}$$

Object Field Access This rule handles access to an instance field f with type τ_f of an object through expressions of the form $o.f : \tau_f$. The object reference o is evaluated to a symbolic reference r_s , which corresponds to a unique concrete reference r_c via the alias map A_S . The corresponding heap object $H_S(r_c)$ is assumed to be of the form $O_{\text{obj}}(\tau, F)$, where F is the field map.

If the field f is already present in F , its value $F(f)$ is returned directly.

$$\frac{s_S = l := o.f : \tau_f \quad \llbracket o \rrbracket_S = r_s \quad r_s \in R_S \quad A_S(r_s) = \{r_c\} \quad H_S(r_c) = O_{\text{obj}}(\tau_0, F) \quad f \in F}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := F(f)]}$$

If the field is not yet defined, i.e., $f \notin F$, a fresh symbolic value is created for it. This situation can occur for heap objects representing arguments of the MUT, as their fields may have been initialized prior to the MUT’s invocation—outside the scope of symbolic execution. As a result, these field values are treated as unknown inputs and are represented symbolically, in line with the core principle of symbolic execution. For primitive type parameters, the rule creates a fresh symbolic variable. For objects or arrays, a new `HeapObject` is allocated on the heap, and a set of potential aliases is constructed for the newly created symbolic reference, consisting of the concrete references to all other heap objects of the same type, along with null. These rules correspond to the lazy initialization mechanic described in Section 4.4.4.

$$\frac{A_S(r_s) = \{r_c\} \quad s_S = l := o.f : \tau_f \quad \llbracket o \rrbracket_S = r_s \quad r_s \in R_S \quad f \notin F \quad \tau_f \in \text{PrimitiveType} \quad e = \text{newVar}(\tau_f)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := e, H \mapsto H_S[r_c \mapsto O_{\text{obj}}(\tau_0, F[f \mapsto e])]]}$$

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} r_s^o \in R_S \quad A_S(r_s^o) = \{r_c^o\} \quad H_S(r_c^o) = O_{\text{obj}}(\tau_o, F) \quad f \notin F \quad \tau_f \in \text{ReferenceType} \\ r_s^f = \text{newRef}() \quad r_c^f = \text{newRef}() \quad O = \text{newObj}(\tau_f) \quad a = \{r_c^f, \text{null}\} \cup \text{findAliases}(\tau_f, H_S) \end{array}}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := r_s^f, H \mapsto H_S[r_c^o \mapsto O_{\text{obj}}(\tau_o, F[f \mapsto r_s^f]), r_c^f \mapsto O], A \mapsto A_S[r_s^f \mapsto a]]}$$

Array Length This rule handles expressions that access the length of an array. The array reference a is expected to point to an array object $O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, E, \ell)$. The symbolic length of the array ℓ is returned as the evaluated expression.

$$\frac{s_S = l := a.\text{length} \quad \llbracket a \rrbracket_S = r_s \quad r_s \in R_S \quad A_S(r_s) = \{r_c\} \quad H_S(r_c) = O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, E, \ell)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := \ell]}$$

Array Indexing This rule handles access to an array's value at index i . The array reference a and index i are evaluated to a symbolic reference r_s and a symbolic expression e_i , respectively. The symbolic reference r_s is resolved to an array object $O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, E, \ell)$. To model the possibility of an out-of-bounds access, the rule produces two successor states:

- One in which a new path constraint enforces that the index is within bound ($0 \leq e_i < \ell$), and the value at index e_i in the symbolic array E is substituted in the assignment statement.
- Another in which the index is out of bounds ($e_i < 0 \vee e_i \geq \ell$), and the exception flag f_{exc} is set to indicate that an exception would be thrown at this point.

$$\frac{s_S = l := a[i] \quad \llbracket a \rrbracket_S = r_s \quad \llbracket i \rrbracket_S = e_i \quad r_s \in R_S \quad A(r_s) = \{r_c\} \quad H(r_c) = O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, E, \ell)}{S \rightarrow \begin{array}{l} S[s \mapsto l := E(e_i), \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{0 \leq e_i < \ell\}], \\ S[\pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{e_i < 0 \vee e_i \geq \ell\}, f_{\text{exc}} \mapsto \top] \end{array}}$$

Method Invocation When a method invocation appears on the right-hand side of an assignment, the method must be executed before its return value can be used. If no return value ρ is present in state S (i.e., $\rho_S = \perp$), it means the method has not been executed yet. In that case, control is delegated to the method being invoked. This follows the same semantics as the rules defined in Section 5.2.1.5, so we omit the details here.

$$\frac{s_S \in \{l := \text{Class}.m(a_0, \dots, a_n), l := o.m(a_0, \dots, a_n)\} \quad \rho_S = \perp}{\text{delegated to method invocation handling}}$$

If a return value ρ is already present in S , it means the method invocation was already completed, and we can substitute the result in the assignment statement.

$$\frac{s_S \in \{l := \text{Class}.m(a_0, \dots, a_n), l := o.m(a_0, \dots, a_n)\} \quad \rho_S = e}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := e]}$$

Parameter Reference Parameter references in Jimple are expressions of the form `param i : τ` , referring to the i^{th} method argument of type τ . If the current method was invoked during symbolic execution following the rules in Section 5.2.1.5, the corresponding parameter values are already

stored in σ_S under canonical variable names arg_i and can be retrieved directly.

$$\frac{s_S = l := \text{param } i : \tau \quad \text{arg}_i \in \sigma_S \sigma_S(\text{arg}_i) = e}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := e]}$$

If, however, the current method is the initial MUT—i.e., the entry point of symbolic execution rather than a method invoked during execution—a fresh symbolic value must be created to represent the unknown input. This mirrors the treatment of uninitialized fields in heap objects: a new symbolic variable or heap object is introduced to stand in for the unknown value. It allows the engine to reason about all possible values of a method parameter.

$$\frac{s_S = l := \text{param } i : \tau \quad \text{arg}_i \notin \sigma_S \quad \tau \in \text{PrimitiveType} \quad e = \text{newVar}(\tau)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := e]}$$

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} r_s = \text{newRef}() \quad s_S = l := \text{param } i : \tau \quad \text{arg}_i \in \sigma_S \quad \tau \in \text{ReferenceType} \\ r_c = \text{newRef}() \quad O = \text{newObj}(\tau) \quad a = \{r_c, \text{null}\} \cup \text{findAliases}(\tau, H_S) \end{array}}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := r_s, H \mapsto H_S[r_c \mapsto O], A \mapsto A_S[r_s \mapsto a]]}$$

Local Variables and Constants This rule covers the base case for right-hand sides in assignment statements. If the right-hand side is a constant or a local variable—i.e., it matches none of the more complex constructs handled by previous rules—its value is determined by evaluating the expression using the evaluation function $\llbracket v \rrbracket_S$.

$$\frac{s_S = l := v \quad \llbracket v \rrbracket_S = e}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := e]}$$

5.2.1.7 Assignment Application

Having evaluated the right-hand side of the assignment using the rules from the previous section, we now assume it has been reduced to a symbolic expression e_v . The rules in this section complete the assignment by applying e_v to the appropriate left-hand side, and advancing execution to the next statement(s). We distinguish three cases based on the form of the left-hand side l : assignment to an array element, assignment to an object field, and assignment to a local variable.

Note that certain combinations of left-hand side and right-hand side expressions, such as both array access operations, will never appear in Jimple due to its three-address code structure. Specifically, Jimple ensures that complex expressions, like array assignments involving array indexing on both sides (e.g., $a[i] = b[j]$), are split into separate statements.

Array Assignment This rule handles assignments to array elements of the form $a[i] = e_v$. As in array indexing, we must check that the index i lies within the bounds of the array. The transition creates two successor states: one in which the index is within bounds and the array is updated accordingly, and one in which the index is out of bounds, triggering an exception.

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \llbracket a \rrbracket_S = r_s \quad \llbracket i \rrbracket_S = e_i \quad r_s \in R_S \quad s_S = a[i] = e_v \\ A(r_s) = \{r_c\} \quad H(r_c) = O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, E, \ell) \quad s' \in \text{succ}(s_S) \end{array}}{S \rightarrow \begin{array}{l} S[s \mapsto s', d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{0 \leq e_i < \ell\}, H \mapsto H_S[r_c \mapsto O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, E[e_i \mapsto e_v], \ell)]], \\ S[\pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{e_i < 0 \vee e_i \geq \ell\}, f_{\text{exc}} \mapsto \top] \end{array}}$$

Object Field Assignment This rule handles assignments to fields of the form $o.f := e_v$, where o is a reference to an object and f is a field of that object. The rule retrieves the heap object associated with o as before. It then updates the heap object by mapping field f to the new symbolic value e_v .

$$\frac{s_S = o.f := e_v \quad \llbracket o \rrbracket_S = r_s \quad r_s \in R_S \quad A(r_s) = \{r_c\} \quad H(r_c) = O_{\text{obj}}(\tau, F) \quad s' \in \text{succ}(s_S)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s', d \mapsto d_S + 1, H \mapsto H_S[r_c \mapsto O_{\text{obj}}(\tau, F[f \mapsto e_v])]]}$$

Local Variable Assignment This rule handles the assignment of a symbolic value e_v to a local variable l . The state transition updates the σ_S by associating l with the new value e_v .

$$\frac{s_S = l := e_v \quad s' \in \text{succ}(s)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s', d \mapsto d_S + 1, \sigma \mapsto \sigma_S[l \mapsto e_v]]}$$

5.2.1.8 Other Statements

For all other statements, such as `nop` or `goto`, the symbolic state remains unchanged except for advancing the current statement to its successor(s), which in most cases consists of a single successor.

$$\frac{s' \in \text{succ}(s_S)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s', d \mapsto d_S + 1]}$$

5.2.2 Symbolic Replay

Instead of exploring all possible paths, symbolic replay follows a specific execution trace, symbolically modeling the behavior of a previous concrete execution. Each transition rule produces a single successor state for a given state S . We define only the rules where symbolic replay differs from standard execution. In all other cases, replay follows the same rules as standard execution.

If Statement The transition rule for `if` statements during symbolic replay follows the path specified by the recorded trace. If the trace entry's value is 1, the true branch is followed; if it is 0, the false branch is taken.

$$\frac{s_S = \text{if } (c) \text{ then } s_t \text{ else } s_f \quad \llbracket c \rrbracket_S = e \quad \text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m_S) = \langle \text{IF}, 1 \rangle}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s_t, d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{e\}]}$$

$$\frac{s_S = \text{if } (c) \text{ then } s_t \text{ else } s_f \quad \llbracket c \rrbracket_S = e \quad \text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m_S) = \langle \text{IF}, 0 \rangle}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s_f, d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{\neg e\}]}$$

Switch Statement The transition rule for `switch` statements during symbolic replay enters only the case specified by the recorded trace. For a `switch` statement with n cases, it follows the i^{th} case if the trace entry's value is $1 \leq i \leq n$, and the default case if it is $n + 1$.

$$\frac{s_S = \text{switch } (k) \{v_1 \Rightarrow s_1, \dots, v_n \Rightarrow s_n, \text{default} \Rightarrow s_d\} \quad \llbracket k \rrbracket_S = e_k \quad \text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m_S) = \langle \text{SWITCH}, i \rangle \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \quad \llbracket v_i \rrbracket_S = e_i}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s_i, d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{e_k = e_i\}]}$$

$$\frac{s_S = \text{switch}(k) \{v_1 \Rightarrow s_1, \dots, v_n \Rightarrow s_n, \text{default} \Rightarrow s_d\} \quad \llbracket k \rrbracket_S = e_k \quad (\llbracket v_i \rrbracket_S = e_i)_{i=1}^n \quad \text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m_S) = \langle \text{SWITCH}, n+1 \rangle}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s_d, d \mapsto d_S + 1, \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{\bigwedge_{i=1}^n e_k \neq e_i\}]}$$

Catching Exceptions States with the exception flag set to true are handled similarly to standard execution, with the key difference that only a single catch block is entered. Execution proceeds to the first catch block encountered, represented as $s' = \varepsilon_S.s \in \text{csucc}(s_S)$. This is a limitation of the engine, as it lacks the instrumentation to tell exactly which catch block was entered during the concrete execution. If no catch block is available, the standard execution rule applies.

$$\frac{f_{\text{exc}} = \top \quad \text{csucc}(s_S) \neq \emptyset \quad s' = \varepsilon_S.s \in \text{csucc}(s_S)}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s', d \mapsto d_S + 1, f_{\text{exc}} \mapsto \perp]}$$

Unexpected End of Trace The engine may reach a decision point where a trace entry is required but missing—typically due to the lack of instrumentation for exception handling. In such cases, it marks the state as exceptional and proceeds accordingly. The same behavior occurs when a trace entry mismatch is detected (e.g., encountering a SWITCH entry at an if statement). The rules for this are relatively straightforward and omitted for brevity.

Parameter Reference As described in Section 4.6, the execution trace records which method arguments are aliases of one another or represent null references. This allows aliasing of method arguments to be resolved deterministically during a symbolic replay. That is, for parameter references that create a new symbolic object or array, aliasing can be resolved immediately using the next trace entry. Such parameter references always appear at the start of the method—precisely where the instrumented MUT performs alias checks and records the trace entry for it.

If the trace entry's value equals the parameter's index, it refers to a distinct heap object.

$$\frac{s_S = l := \text{param } i : \tau \quad \text{arg}_i \in \sigma_S \quad \tau \in \text{ReferenceType} \quad r_s = \text{newRef}() \quad \text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m_S) = \langle \text{ALIAS}, j \rangle \quad i = j \quad r_c = \text{newRef}() \quad O = \text{newObj}(\tau) \quad a = \{r_c\}}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := r_s, H \mapsto H_S[r_c \mapsto O], A \mapsto A_S[r_s \mapsto a]]}$$

If the trace entry's value is -1 , the parameter is a null reference.

$$\frac{\tau \in \text{ReferenceType} \quad s_S = l := \text{param } i : \tau \quad \text{arg}_i \in \sigma_S \quad r_s = \text{newRef}() \quad \text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m_S) = \langle \text{ALIAS}, -1 \rangle \quad a = \{\text{null}\}}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := r_s, A \mapsto A_S[r_s \mapsto a]]}$$

Otherwise, the parameter is an alias of another parameter with a lower index, which must thus already have been resolved.

$$\frac{s_S = l := \text{param } i : \tau \quad \text{arg}_i \in \sigma_S \quad \tau \in \text{ReferenceType} \quad r_s = \text{newRef}() \quad \text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m_S) = \langle \text{ALIAS}, j \rangle \quad i \neq j \quad A_S(\text{arg}_j) = r_c \quad a = \{r_c\}}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := r_s, A \mapsto A_S[r_s \mapsto a]]}$$

Alias Resolution While the engine can deterministically resolve aliasing among method arguments, as defined by the previous rule, it does not instrument the CUT to detect whether arbitrary objects encountered during execution alias other arbitrary objects—such general alias detection would be exceedingly complex to implement, and was considered out of scope. Thus, we apply an approximation by resolving such aliasing by picking the first non-null alias from the symbolic reference’s alias map entry, which we denote $r_c = \varepsilon r.(r \in A_S(r_s) \wedge r \neq \text{null})$.

$$\frac{r_s = \text{uref}(S) \quad r_c = \varepsilon r.r \in (A_S(r_s) \wedge r \neq \text{null})}{S \rightarrow S[\pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{r_s = r_c\}, A \mapsto A_S[r_s \mapsto \{r_c\}], R \mapsto R_S \cup \{r_s\}]}$$

End of Constructor Handling When execution reaches the end of the CUT’s constructor, the only deviation from standard execution is that control proceeds directly to the single method m targeted by the symbolic replay rather than to every non-static method of the CUT. Due to its simplicity, the rule is omitted.

Array Indexing In standard execution, array indexing on the right-hand side of an assignment splits the state into two branches: one assuming the index is within bounds, and one assuming it is out of bounds. In symbolic replay, this branching is guided by the trace, which records whether the index was in or out of bounds during the concrete execution. If the trace entry’s value is 1, the index is treated as in-bounds; if it is 0, it is treated as out-of-bounds.

$$\frac{\llbracket i \rrbracket_S = e_i \quad r_s \in R_S \quad \begin{array}{l} s_S = l := a[i] \\ A(r_s) = \{r_c\} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \llbracket a \rrbracket_S = r_s \\ H(r_c) = O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, E, \ell) \end{array} \quad \text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m_S) = \langle \text{ARRAY}, 1 \rangle}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto l := E(e_i), \pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{0 \leq e_i < \ell\}]}$$

$$\frac{\llbracket i \rrbracket_S = e_i \quad r_s \in R_S \quad \begin{array}{l} s_S = l := a[i] \\ A(r_s) = \{r_c\} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \llbracket a \rrbracket_S = r_s \\ H(r_c) = O_{\text{arr}}(\tau, E, \ell) \end{array} \quad \text{take}(\mathcal{T}, m_S) = \langle \text{ARRAY}, 0 \rangle}{S \rightarrow S[\pi \mapsto \pi_S \cup \{e_i < 0 \vee e_i \geq \ell\}, f_{\text{exc}} \mapsto \top]}$$

Array Assignment Array assignment follows the same trace-based decision process to determine whether the index is in bounds as the previous rule for array indexing. The remainder of the rule mirrors the standard execution array assignment behavior and is omitted here for brevity.

Other Statements In symbolic replay, execution follows only a single successor statement. Whereas standard execution explores all successors $s \in \text{succ}(s_S)$, symbolic replay selects the first successor that is not in a catch block. This guarantees a unique successor, as multiple successors only occur within try-catch blocks, or constructs already handled by previous rules. Rules from standard execution that apply during replay are assumed to adopt this deterministic successor selection and are not restated here.

$$\frac{s' = \varepsilon s.(s \in \text{succ}(s_S) \wedge s \notin \text{csucc}(s_S))}{S \rightarrow S[s \mapsto s', d \mapsto d_S + 1]}$$